

RESEARCH METHODS OF PROFESSIONAL PEDAGOGY

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Abstract. *This article briefly touches on the general aspects of the methodology. In the dictionaries, methodology is given as a teaching about the scientific method of knowledge, as a teaching about the principles and ways of organizing theoretical and practical activities, about the methods used in this or that discipline,*

Key words: *pedagogy, method, dialectic, analysis, theory, teaching, questionnaire method.*

МЕТОДЫ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЙ ПЕДАГОГИКИ

Аннотация. *В данной статье кратко затронуты общие аспекты методологии. В словарях методология дается как учение о научном методе познания, как учение о принципах и способах организации теоретической и практической деятельности, о методах, используемых в той или иной дисциплине,*

Ключевые слова: *педагогика, метод, диалектика, анализ, теория, обучение, анкетный метод.*

Without mastering the methodological foundations of any science, it is impossible to understand the essence of the field of scientific knowledge of this science and its practical application. Let's briefly touch on the general conditions of scientific methodology. In dictionaries, methodology is defined as a teaching about the scientific method of knowledge, as a teaching about the principles and ways of organizing theoretical and practical activities, as a set of methods used in one or another discipline. explained. There is a philosophical and special scientific level of methodology. The highest level of science methodology is philosophy. As we know, dialectical materialism was adopted as the philosophical basis of science education during the former Shura regime. Therefore, many experts believe that dialectics is the philosophical foundation of social, humanitarian and natural sciences. According to them, the rules of dialectics are common to the educational and training processes in the entire pedagogical system. Therefore, the necessary philosophical theories are interconnected with any science. In philosophy, ideas and principles, laws and regularities, concepts and categories are accepted as attributes of science. Among the ideas of dialectical materialism, we will consider the principles of determinism, that is, the interrelationship and development of events. The principle of development in pedagogy means that the pedagogical process is a social and complex phenomenon consisting of educational and training processes. It includes all components: the needs of society and the goal of education, pedagogue and students, the material to be mastered and the ways of its transmission, training under the guidance of the teacher and independent work of students, educational and educational work. there is a correlation. Thus, the methodology of pedagogy is based on the philosophical and special scientific methodological levels of science. All levels of the methodology are interconnected and interdependent, forming a system. It is necessary for a teacher to know the essence of the methodology of pedagogy in order to effectively organize and manage the educational process. Any science can develop only if it is filled with new knowledge. The

objectivity of obtaining knowledge depends on the choice of research methodology. Methodology (from Greek. *methodos* — theory, doctrine, way of knowing or research and *logos* — word, concept): 1) a system of principles and ways of building and organizing practical and theoretical activities; 2) teaching about the scientific method of knowledge; 3) means a set of methods used in one or another science. The methodology of the science of pedagogy is a teaching about the forms, methods and principles of changing pedagogical existence and knowledge processes. The science methodology describes the components of research, forms ideas about the sequence and stages of actions in the process of solving research tasks, describes the set of methods and tools of research, its tasks, the object and subject of research. General theoretical methods in the organization of pedagogical research: analysis, synthesis, comparison, induction, deduction, abstraction, generalization, concretization, modeling; sociological methods: questionnaire, interview, rating; social psychological methods: sociometry, test, training; mathematical methods. Pedagogical research methods are divided into theoretical and practical (empirical) types. Theoretical methods of research require the systematization, expansion, and determination of scientific facts, explain and interpret phenomena in advance, increase the reliability of obtained results, move from abstract to concrete knowledge, establish connections between different concepts and hypotheses, and distinguish between primary and secondary ones. We describe some theoretical methods. Analysis is the separation of phenomena into separate qualities and characteristics, that is, the study of a whole phenomenon or process is mentally divided into component parts. The phenomenon under study can be analyzed from different aspects. Comprehensive analysis represents an in-depth analysis of the essence of the phenomenon. Synthesis is the creation of a whole by combining the properties and qualities of the phenomenon. Synthesis is not only a quantitative collection, but also a meaningful connection. If events are simply connected, then systematic relationships are not formed. Analysis and synthesis are inextricably linked in any research. Comparison - establishing similarities and differences between the studied phenomena. When comparing, it depends on the goal to determine the basis of comparison, that is, the criteria. In order to compare the phenomena with each other, it is necessary to distinguish their main features. The component of comparison is always analysis, and in some cases synthesis is also used. Generalization - separation of common aspects of events and processes. Summary of research. As a result of comparing the phenomena with each other, the researcher finds the common aspects of the phenomena and unites them into one ideological group based on it. Modeling is the study of phenomena and processes using real and ideal models. Induction, deduction are logical methods summarizing information obtained by practical methods. The inductive method means going from specific thoughts to general conclusions, and the deductive method means drawing specific conclusions from the general. Empirical (practical) methods of research include: data collection and collection methods (observation, interview, questionnaire, test); control and measurement methods; data processing methods (mathematical, statistical, graphic, tabular; assessment methods (self-assessment, rating); methods of applying research results in pedagogical practice (experiment, experiential education, large-scale application) and b. Let's consider some methods. Observation is a purposeful, systematic study of specific pedagogical phenomena. Observation is widely used in the science of pedagogy. As the main method of collecting scientific materials, observation is an auxiliary method in some cases.

Observation itself Along with observation, an ancient research method is felt. Observation as a research method has a number of characteristics:

- the direction of observation; - analytical nature of observation; - the transmitter separates from the general picture its separate aspects, elements, connections, which are evaluated, analyzed, explained; - the complexity (integrity) of the observation, not avoiding the aspects of the observed object; - the systematicity of observation. According to different signs, monitoring is divided into the following types: Monitoring is divided into continuous and discrete types according to the time of establishment. According to the scope of observation, it is divided into broad and narrow types of observation. According to the ways of obtaining data, surveillance is divided into direct and covert surveillance. According to the difference between the observer and the observed, it is divided into continuous and periodic observation. According to the conditions of conducting, it is divided into natural and experimental observation. Informal (free) and formal (standard) observation according to the plan. Depending on the period of use, it is divided into permanent, returnable, one-time, and multiple monitoring. The types of monitoring depend on the purpose and the nature of the object. Like any method, tracking has its pros and cons. Positive aspects of the observation method: - studies the subject as a whole; - learning in natural conditions; - learns in multifaceted communication and manifestation. Disadvantages of this method: - inability to cover a large number of events; - it takes a lot of time; - the possibility of errors related to the observer's identity; • not being able to observe certain events and processes. Pedagogical observation is a passive form of scientific research.

The questionnaire method is based on the organization of communication with the respondents based on systematic questions, with the help of this method the evidence collected during the pedagogical observation and interview process is enriched. The questionnaire method is effectively used if the following conditions are followed: 1) if the questions of the questionnaire serve to clarify the essence of the problem; 2) questionnaire questions should not be large and vague; 3) questionnaire questions are created taking into account students' outlook, age, and psychological characteristics; 4) allocating enough time for full answers to the questions; 5) the questionnaire should not become a source of pedagogical and psychological descriptions of students; 6) to analyze the answers to the questionnaire questions based on certain criteria. The test method is a short standard test used to determine and evaluate the level of mental development, ability, skills, abilities, personal and willful qualities, mental characteristics of the person being studied, and its significance is the person's theoretical knowledge in a specific field, the development of abilities, psychophysiological, personal characteristics, the ability to organize a certain activity, is noticeable in determining the level of formation of skills. The scientific-practical importance of the pedagogical experiment method is reflected in the creation of ample opportunities for studying the possibilities of finding a solution to the problem, the ability of the existing pedagogical conditions to guarantee the achievement of the goal, the ability to have their own opinion of the given recommendations in practice, and to determine their effectiveness. It is one of the research methods and represents the conversion of qualitative factors into a quantitative series. The method of mathematical-statistical analysis is conducted in order to systematically study, generalize and assess the validity of practical results based on a specific goal of pedagogical research, practical results of experimental work. The purpose of using the mathematical-statistical

method in pedagogical scientific research is to determine the level of effectiveness of experimental work and research work. According to it, the indicators obtained at the beginning and at the end of the experiment in the experimental and control groups are re-analyzed using special mathematical formulas, the final value is the main indicator representing the effectiveness of the research. 1.7. The connection of vocational pedagogy with other subjects. The curriculum for training teachers of vocational education envisages the implementation of subjects in the blocks of humanitarian and socio-economic, mathematical and natural-scientific, general professional, specialization, additional and elective subjects. . It is possible to divide the block of general professional subjects into psychological-pedagogical, design-construction-technological, operational (service), construction courses. Psychological-pedagogical preparation of teachers of vocational education includes such subjects as youth physiology and hygiene, psychology, pedagogy, pedagogy of vocational education, pedagogical skills, pedagogical technologies, methodology of vocational education, guidance for choosing a profession in the psychological-pedagogical category. is realized in relational learning. "Vocational education pedagogy" is one of the specialization subjects in the training of a vocational education teacher. This science does not repeat other sciences (pedagogy, psychology, methods of vocational education, guidance for choosing a profession, etc.), but is in close contact with them. Therefore, the science of "Professional pedagogy" cannot be imagined without the knowledge gained in other psychological-pedagogical disciplines. It is impossible to deeply master the science of "Vocational Education Pedagogy" without studying the science of some psychological-pedagogical series and acquiring the knowledge in them. While studying the subject of "Pedagogy of Vocational Education", the future teacher of vocational education should have studied a number of the following subjects, he should have acquired deep knowledge of these subjects:

- object, tasks of general psychology. Psychology as a natural and social science. Psyche, an understanding of, the task of guidance and control. Brain and psyche. Psyche and consciousness. Psychology and philosophy. Psychological views of Eastern thinkers. Fundamentals of Psyche and Mind Analysis. The structure of modern psychology and its foundations. Fields of psychology.

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